

COMPOSITE DISC
A Slide Rule for Calculating the most important Composite Engineering Constants

W. Michaeli, M. Wegener, D. Huybrechts
Institute for Plastics Processing (IKV)
Aachen, Germany

ABSTRACT

Up to now, the engineering constants (Young's modulus, strength and strain limit) of a laminate, in virtually all of the cases, had to be calculated using a program. For the purpose of quick predimensioning the IKV recently introduced the Composite Disc, which stands for a new possibility of estimating the main properties, i.e. the longitudinal tensile Young's Modulus and strength of multilayer laminates. This is enabled by a modification of the classical laminate theory and realized in the Composite Disc for laminates made from UD layers of the four most usual high-performance fibre reinforced plastics GFRP, CFRP-HT, CFRP-HM and AFRP with any number of layers with any number of orientation angle and any combination of the four materials. As the only precondition, the laminate must be orthotropic and symmetrical, i.e. must be a usual balanced compound.

Keywords: Composite Disc, predimensioning, tensile Young's Modulus, tensile strength, modified/restricted classical laminate theory, high-performance reinforced plastics

1. INTRODUCTION

Mainly by their outstanding lightweight construction properties, i.e. their excellent strength and stiffness related to weight properties high-performance fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) are particularly appropriated as constructional materials for High Tech applications. In this field laminates of assembled UD layers are principally used.

At the state of the art the anisotropic laminate properties resulting from this configuration are calculated by means of the classical laminate theory (CLT) /1,2/. The principle of the calculation theory is admittedly simple, but the calculating operation is relatively extensive and complex. Therefore the determination of laminate properties, even for a roughly estimation, supposes the use of a computer.

This is disadvantageous in the industrial practice above all in the very first phase of design of a FRP part. The phase of finding out concepts is often realized by brainstorming and only rough estimations of the dimensioning are made. In these phase, on one hand, "exact" laminate properties are not required. The only point is the possibility to make ratings. On the other hand the use of a computer is not usual and even inconvenient in this workingsphere.

That is why an alternative contrivance was developed at the IKV. It excels by its simple handling and by giving results quickly (fig.1).

Figure 1, Composite Disc

2. CALCULATION THEORIES

At the design phase of finding out concepts the in plane stiffness and strength are the most essential properties of the laminate for the constructing engineer.

The realization of the Composite Disc was made possible by a simplification of the CLT and some other assumptions /3, 4/ for the uniaxial tensile state of stress shown in fig. 2.

Figure 2, Laminate definitions and stress state

2.1 Approximation of the longitudinal laminate tensile Young's Modulus

The calculation of the engineering constant Young's Modulus is simplified by considering the different layers of the laminate also individually. The Young's Modulus of a laminate in the load direction (fig.2) can be determined by adding the Young's Modulus of all the single layers in this direction pondered with the part of the cross section of the layers.

$$E_{x, Lam} = \sum \left(E_{x, Lay} \cdot \frac{t_{Lay}}{t_{Lam}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Corresponding to this approximation, you may imagine the laminate as sort of a parallel consideration of the individual layers.

Similar to the procedure in the CLT for a laminate the Young's Modulus of a single layer is determined as reciprocal constant of the first element of the single layer compliance matrix S_{xx}

$$E_x = \frac{1}{S_{xx}} \quad (2)$$

whereby S_{xx} can be determined from the elements of the single layer stiffness matrix $[Q]$

$$S_{xx} = \frac{Q_{11}Q_{22}Q_{33} - Q_{12}^2Q_{33}}{m^4Q_{22}Q_{33} - m^2n^2(2Q_{12}Q_{33} - Q_{11}Q_{22} + Q_{12}^2) + n^4Q_{11}Q_{33}} \quad (3)$$

The difference between this modification and the "exact" CLT is therefore only, that for the determination of the Young's Modulus here the properties of the single layers are added up, whereas for the CLT first the laminate stiffness matrix A has to be established before it can be inverted to the laminate compliance matrix a .

The error resulting from the described approximation compared to the CLT is due to the fact, that the supporting effect, which is resulting from the firm junction of the single layers which in its turn impedes the transversal contraction, in this case is neglected. Thus as to its properties of stiffness the laminate is underestimated.

Improvement of this approximation:

Since generally the laminate has a symmetric, i.e. an orthotropic structure, to each layer with a positive angle of orientation there will be a layer with a corresponding negativ angle of orientation. In the simplified theory of calculation as described above this fact can be used to improve the approximation. Instead of considering all the layers individually, the layers with the same angles of orientation, but different operational sign can be considered together as firmly joined by determining the stiffness matrix for the two symmetrical layers as follows.

$$[Q_{+/-}] = \frac{1}{2} \cdot ([Q_{+}] + [Q_{-}]) \tag{4}$$

In this way the number of the terms of the sum for the determination by approximation of the Young's Modulus is reduced, because the supporting effect of the firmly joined layers is partially taken into consideration.

The following figure 3 shows the error of this improved approximation compared to the "exact" CLT by means of a Carpet plot for the relatively typical $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$ laminates, layed up with GFRP UD layers.

In this figure the maximal error of the approximation comes up to 20 % for a laminate configuration without 0° , i.e. without layers in the considered direction. But in the practical application the load direction will be identical with the considered direction in most of the cases so that there will be a relatively high part of 0° layers. For these laminate configurations the error will be substantially lower.

Figure 3, Carpet plot for $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$ GFRP laminates

But here it should be repeated once more, that the stiffness of the laminate in any way is underestimated, i.e. the rough estimation of the dimensioning is "on the safe side".

2.2 Approximation of longitudinal laminate tensile strength

Besides the question of the stiffness of a laminate, its strength is, of course, also of importance for a rough dimensioning. In order to have the possibility to determine approximatively the strength of a laminate for an uniaxial tensile load (fig. 2) the method of calculation developed in /4/ is used.

By means of the Young's Modulus already known (chap. 2.1) and the limiting laminate strain $\epsilon_{x,lim}$ in the load direction the laminate tensile strength X can be calculated with the Hooke's law for this case.

$$X = E_x \cdot \epsilon_{x,lim} \quad (5)$$

To determine the limiting laminate strain is taken advantage of the assumption of the CLT, that, relative to the global coordinate system of the laminate, all layers of a laminate undergo the same dilatation. Comparing the layers, the one with the lowest limiting strain in the load direction has to be determined. Therefore the maximum strain criterion developed in /5/ is used in connection with the calculation method developed in /4/, which leads to the following function.

$$\epsilon_{x,lim} = \min \left\{ \frac{\epsilon_1}{m^2 + \frac{s_{12}}{s_{11}} n^2}; \frac{\epsilon_2}{n^2 + \frac{s_{12}}{s_{11}} m^2}; \frac{\gamma_{12}}{\left(1 - \frac{s_{12}}{s_{11}}\right) 2mn} \right\} \quad (6)$$

As can be understood from the resulting function courses of the limiting strain, which as example is figured over the angle of orientation for GFRP in figure 4, the relevant limit of strain is determined by the layer with the highest angle of orientation (as far as the layers of the laminate are all of the same material).

In figure 4 distinction is made between "critical" and "ultimate" strain. Which of both limits is chosen depends on dimensioning against microcracks (critical) or against failure (ultimate) of this layer.

The calculation error made by approximating the strength of a laminate is just as large as by approximating the Young's Modulus, i.e. it is underestimated in the same range.

Figure 4, Limiting strain for a UD GFRP layer

3. REALIZATION OF THE COMPOSITE DISC

Based on the above described approximations the Composite Disc as shown in figure 1 was developed as a kind of slide rule in the shape of a parking disc.

It is based on 4 typical high-performance FRP materials for UD layers with 50, 60 and 70 percent fibre volume contents. Their material specifications are shown in the tables below.

FRP Material	Fibre cont. (Vol . %)	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{21}
GFRP	50	37.0	8.9	4.5	0.29
	60	44.5	12.5	6.0	0.28
	70	52.0	18.0	8.3	0.27
CFRP-HT	50	108.0	8.9	5.2	0.31
	60	130.0	9.5	5.6	0.30
	70	150.0	10.3	6.4	0.29
CFRP-HM	50	208.0	7.2	4.8	0.29
	60	250.0	7.5	5.5	0.28
	70	290.0	7.8	6.5	0.27
AFRP	50	67.0	5.0	2.5	0.37
	60	80.0	5.2	2.7	0.36
	70	93.0	5.4	3.0	0.35

Table 1, Stiffness properties of UD layers

FRP Material	critical			ultimate		
	ϵ_1	ϵ_2	γ_{12}	ϵ_1	ϵ_2	γ_{12}
GFRP	0.80	0.10	0.20	2.90	0.30	1.20
CFRP-HT	0.60	0.20	0.40	1.10	0.50	1.20
CFRP-HM	0.20	0.20	0.30	0.45	0.45	0.90
AFRP	0.60	0.10	0.20	1.80	0.28	1.20

Table 2, Strain limits for UD layers

The Composite Disc is provided with a modulus-side and a stress/strain-side, which allow determining in a very simple and quick way the above described approximations for the materials defined in the tables by positioning several discs one against the other.

Referring to the laminate lay up, the only restriction is, that it must be an orthotropic, i.e. a usual balanced compound. It may have any number of layers with any number of orientation angle in any combination of the four materials.

The accuracy of the Composite Disc increases with increasing part of layers with small orientation angles. On average, an underestimation of 10 % is made, but in many cases, however, the data determined are much better.

Acknowledgements

The results presented in this paper were achieved with the financial aid of the Arbeitsgemeinschaft Industrieller Forschungsvereinigungen e.V. (AiF) and the German Federal Ministry of Trade and Commerce. We thank these institutions.

References

- /1/ Tsai, S., *Composite Design*, Think Composites, 3rd Edition, Dayton-Paris-Tokio, 1987
- /2/ Geier, B., *Grundlagen der Strukturmechanischen Berechnung von Bauteilen aus Faserverbundwerkstoffen*, Leichtbau mit Kohlenstofffaserverstärkten Kunststoffen, Kontakt und Studium Band 167, Expert Verlag, Sindelfingen 1985
- /3/ Wegener, M., *Strategien zum werkstoffgerechten Entwurf von Bauteilen aus Faserverbundkunststoffen*, Dissertation an der RWTH Aachen (D82), Verlag der Augustinus Buchhandlung, Aachen, 1992
- /4/ Effing, M., *Rechnerunterstützte Auslegung und Fertigung von Faserverbundbauteilen*, Dissertation an der RWTH Aachen, 1988
- /5/ Brintrup, H., *Ein Beitrag zum zeitabhängigen Verformungsverhalten und zur Rißbildung orthotrop glasfaserverstärkter Polyesterharze unter ebener Normalbeanspruchung*, Dissertation an der RWTH Aachen, 1975